

Audio file

[audio1329762976.m4a](#)

Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, my name is Anna Makarudze, and I'm pursuing a Master's in Software Engineering at Clean Institute of Technology. I'm investigating how developers in Manila perceive vulnerabilities in open source dependencies they include in their projects, especially with regards to the rise of supply chain attacks. And I'm focusing on developers from 5 ecosystems. Python, mainly focusing on Django, then JavaScript, mainly focusing on Nick JS, Java, focusing on Spring Boot, PHP, focusing on Laravel, and then Ruby, focusing Ruby on Rails. Participation in this is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time. We will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. Your name, your role, e-mail address, and any other identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions you're not comfortable answering and your responses will remain anonymous and will not be linked to you or the projects that you represent. The interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow supervisors to verify the authenticity of reported data, after which they will be deleted and will in compliance with the GDPR regulation.

So we can start by you introducing yourself, telling us whether you are a developer, contributor, or a maintainer of the web framework that you use. And also, if you are maintaining any other frameworks, any other software based on that framework, you can also mention them. You can tell me about your role, your job title, as well as how many years of experience you have in the software development industry, or how many years of experience you have with that web framework.

Speaker 2

So I'm an engineer, software developer with over 10 years experience in software development. I've worked with pretty much most of the frameworks that you mentioned, but my primary focus in the last seven years has been with Ruby and Ruby on Rails.

My current role is a senior software engineer at a company within the open science community building infrastructure to support the research institution for what we call DOI registrations.

And I think my day-to-day, it's mainly addressing technical debt for the applications, doing robust upgrades of the infrastructure that we support, and diving deeper into the anatomy of Ruby and the Rails framework.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And in your role, can you specify more? Do you contribute to code? Do you test? Do you triage? Or do you review and make pull requests? Or maybe you do development? Do you decide also on security issues?

Speaker 2

We do end to end. So the company comprises of mainly senior engineers. So what you get, it's very, I don't want to say vague requirements, but it's a wish from the stakeholders about what they want to have within the system.

So you are responsible, rather, I'm responsible for mapping out the requirements for that particular feature or the particular task that I have and see it from end to end. That is the implementation, the testing, the deployment as well, and also ensuring that it does conform with basic security standards.

Speaker 1

And the project that you're describing, is it governed by a corporate company, or is it a nonprofit like open source?

Speaker 2

It is open source. Everything, it's open source and GitHub, yeah.

Speaker 1

And does it have community contributors?

Speaker 2

Not really. We were sort of trying to get to that space. But the challenge is the initial design did not have the community to contribute in the first place. So there are still a lot of things that are very coupled to only allow internal members to contribute. But the code itself, it's open source. Anyone can run it. But the blocker would be, you know, some private. Key is to certain services that they might not be able to spin it up, but lately we're trying to get to a

point where we can allow the community to make contributions because everything is open source.

Speaker 1

Thank you. Are there any? That you already said you did to end of end to end for security issues. So I'll keep this one. Okay, so in your project, do you rely on other ecosystems, like maybe say JavaScript or Python, Java, Ruby, or is just Ruby in Rails completely?

Speaker 2

Yes, yes, we do rely on other ecosystems. We do have a couple of front-end projects. I think the oldest that we have, it's written in Amber JS and some of the newer ones. They are written in no in next Js. And we also have some data layers where we do a bit of data engineering, and that's mainly in Python.

Speaker 1

And then, how are security issue reports managed in your project? Suppose the security vulnerability that has been discovered some more.

Speaker 2

So it's, I would say it's multifaceted. First part is we, because everything is open source, we do give everyone access to everything. I think with the exception of our infrastructure. But any security vulnerabilities, more specifically around the frameworks themselves, We do keep up to date with the patches that they release, and we ensure that we have that. I think on the projects, we do have Dependabot, which is quite a good tool that we use to keep us up to date with most of these vulnerabilities. We also follow the communities for this particular frameworks that we use to just check if we have anything that might expose us to your security vulnerabilities.

As much as we have a layer that blocks access to our infrastructure, it's also possible that, you know, the framework itself could be a leakage into that internal, into, you know, our internal of the infrastructure. So we try as much as possible to keep patches up to date for the frameworks.

I think on the infrastructure side, we're not too worried because we use third parties, we use AWS for hosting. So it does handle pretty much, I'd say, the bulk of the security for the infrastructure, be it your database access, your server accesses.

Most of it, it's handled from AWS. You obviously have to tighten it up a little bit, but most of it is handled there. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Okay. And How conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your project?

Speaker 2

Can you come?

Speaker 1

I'm saying, how conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your project as a developer?

Speaker 2

I'm very conscious. I think my experience, besides the current company, I've worked in a banking setup. So banking set up any financial institution, it's security first. So I'm very much aware. And as much as I'm working in an open source project, but I think that habit of developing anything with security in mind doesn't go away. So I'm very, very conscious about the security. And I think most of the upgrades that are done within the organization, that role falls under me.

because I sort of do enjoy like patching up things and just getting things into their current state, secure as well. So I think it's just a habit that I picked up in my career just to be very secure when you're building anything.

So I'm very conscious about it.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And how aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects?

Speaker 2

Very much. I think evident mostly in the JavaScript community. They have had very unfortunate couple of months, you know, with the attacks on NPM and leakages. So we very much aware of the supply chain attacks and we try to keep up to date with with information.

I think one of the proactive thing that we try and do is to minimize the number of libraries that we consume from outside that we don't know and don't understand. So we we try to keep everything to a minimum of any third party or any supply that we get from, you know, elsewhere and try to write stuff from our own.

We don't reinvent the wheel when we can we just use stuff from outside. But we also become very proactive in looking at the source codes and just checking everything to make sure that we do not accidentally fall victim to any supply chain attacks.

Speaker 1

Thank you. What influences the decision to update to new applications of the Dependency of the Dinia project? Do you update simply because there's a newer version or?

Speaker 2

So we we we patch things up regularly. The minor patches and the bigger version jumps. That one is dependent on, because we always try to make sure that we are on the latest long term support for any particular vision.

So most of these with Ruby and also rails. They give you a timeframe of this is when the like end of support gets to. So we use those dates to sort of create milestones within the organization to say, by this time we should have migrated from this particular version to the next version.

But in terms of the smaller version patches, like a small bug fix that might not affect us, but the library has patched, those ones, we do them on a regular basis. As soon as we get anything from Dependabot, we get an engineer to review the PR and see if it makes any sense, whether we need to upgrade that particular gem or we don't, do we still need it in the project where we can just remove it completely?

So I would say for minor versions, that's very regular. Then the big version jumps, it is controlled by the frameworks ecosystem as to when they stop supporting it. But yeah, we just try to, you know, get everything ready before the end of support.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And how do you track the maintenance of dependencies in your projects? Like it's it's common for and creators of open source projects to leave them because maybe they no longer have the bandwidth to maintain them and their projects become abandoned. So how do you check to see whether all the gems that you're using in your projects are still being maintained or?

Speaker 2

So that's a very, it's a good point. And also, you know, one of the downsides within the open source where you pick up a gem seven years ago, it works in your system, everything it's, you know, coupled around it. And then seven years later, you cannot still use it because maybe the Ruby version, it's no longer supported by that particular version.

So for us, it's as long as it still works, we keep it. Because once it's published to the Ruby gems, it stays there. So if we pin it to a particular version, we can still use it. However, projects that have publicly announced that they are no longer maintaining them, or maybe one of the features that was being supported by that particular gem has been incorporated into the actual framework.

So there's no need for that particular gem. When we do the bigger version jumps, we do reassess each and every gem that is within the project to see where are we using it? Is it still relevant? Maybe is there something in Rails, the newer version, that does the same thing that we just need to remove or not?

Then we can just, you know, remove that. And I think, funny enough, that's what I'm actually busy with now. I'm upgrading the entire infrastructure. I think it's about 15 repositories. And that's what I actually do, like going through each individual gem, checking where we use it and where we don't use it, and whether we can simply use the vanilla Ruby syntax to just write something up.

Because seven years ago, it made sense. But now it probably doesn't make any sense because it's just maybe three, four lines that you can write and remove the gem completely. So we do keep track of the gems that we use, the maintainability, and their longevity. But for those that we cannot remove, we just try to pin them to the specific versions that are latest and they are paged correctly.

And we use it until we can move away from them. We just classify that other technical debt that we need to address to either rewrite that particular implementation entirely and decouple it so that the entire project is not dependent on that.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. And how do you handle vulnerable dependencies? Maybe they have

Speaker 2

We replace, we replace them. Like I said, it's a case to case. There are some gems or dependencies that are very critical within the community where their implementation hardly changes, but the maintainers are long gone, but their implementation is still relevant.

So we have two options in that case. If it's not too big of a project, we can make a fork and publish it under our organization and maintain it. But if it's too big and we feel that we can do away with it, we just replace it. But we have a couple of gems that we felt were

necessary within the ecosystem. The maintainers, them abandoning them was not really a choice.

Some of them either just lost interest, moved on. Some sadly, the maintainers had passed away. So we sort of just checked that we didn't excuse me the ecosystem within our ecosystem, just make a fork and start maintaining it from there.

Speaker 1

And how long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Honestly, with a lot of automation from Dependabot, I would say a day, because it's just literally reviewing the PRs from those dependencies. But bigger ones where it's a version jump, that one has to be properly planned because it might be introducing some breaking changes within the code, failing tests. But for the minor dependency updates, that's like just a couple of hours to a day, just reviewing the PRs and merging them and doing releases. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you. So you've already mentioned that for dependencies within your ecosystem, Ruby on Rails, sometimes you take over the abandoned project that you have to rely on.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

Then how difficult is this when the dependency is outside of your ecosystems? You already say you use some dependency from JavaScript. So for example, a duplicated JavaScript library that is being used in a project, how then to handle that. Because maybe it might be difficult, but...

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

Excuse it may not be in your...

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

...gem, which you can easily take off.

Speaker 2

With JavaScript, my honest answer would be, it's very messy. And my experience there is very limited. And it's by design because it's too messy for me. I think we do have a project that was dependent, a React project that doesn't work anymore with some of the deployments that we have. We couldn't upgrade it because it was a mere rewrite into a different framework because we couldn't just upgrade it.

So I would say in such instances, it's mostly a rewrite. But yeah, my experience with JavaScript, it's very, very limited due to its messy nature. Yes.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And what practices and tools are in place for supply chain tax mitigation for your project?

Speaker 2

I'm sorry, can you repeat the last part?

Speaker 1

I'm saying what practices and tools have you put in place for mitigation of supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

So we do have CI that runs and we do have some, there are, funny enough, it's a bunch of gems that check vulnerabilities in other gems. So during CI, they run and then they check the versions that you have and if there are any vulnerabilities and it blocks an imaging of that PR if the dependencies that you have have any vulnerabilities that might, you know, cause any attacks.

Speaker 1

Have any of the projects you worked on being exposed to supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

Not really, no. No, I don't think anyone has the time to attack any open source projects because everything is just free. It's it's too much of an effort for things that you can just get.

So we we haven't had any yeah, no, we haven't been exposed to any attacks that we, yeah, no.

Speaker 1

And what features help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Can you rephrase it?

Speaker 1

Okay, I'm saying, okay, what, okay, let me see. What helps you to address vulnerable dependencies within your project? Because sometimes the other person was, what challenges do you face in which you are in addressing vulnerable dependencies? So the opposite of that, what aids you in addressing vulnerable dependencies?

Speaker 2

OK. I think being proactive, being intentional about the code that you introduce into the project, being mindful that they are attacks as much as we are in the open source, and no one really cares to attack any open source project, but just being mindful of those vulnerabilities, and also putting into place measures like the dependable.

Like I said, it does a very good job in scanning the projects regularly, most likely on a daily basis, to check off any identified vulnerabilities in any patches that are available. If there are none, it does still notify you that something.

But with our CI, when we build and do deployments, we we get notified that a particular gem has a serious vulnerability. Either where there isn't any patch.

In that case we can just monkey patch that particular gem until whatever latest version there is, and we can just replace or remove the monkey patch with the updates to that particular gem. But I think the biggest one is just being proactive and being mindful and intentional with your code.

Speaker 1

And what challenges you face when you're addressing these vulnerable dependencies?

Speaker 2

They can be too many and too noisy. Some of them are very small things that really you don't need to worry about. So we don't always address them every day. We do that once in a month. We used to try and address them like on a daily basis.

But we just felt like, yeah, we were almost likely just gonna spend entire time trying to patch up things. So if it's not a big vulnerability, the priority, it's low. We can just leave it there and do that maybe once a week or once a month.

Speaker 1

So what you just want to clarify what you're saying is too noisy. It's good up to end up with.

Speaker 2

Yeah, yeah, yeah, it can be too noisy, because every day, there's always one or more vulnerabilities that are picked up. So depending on if it's set, it notifies you of pretty much all of that. So that can get a little bit noisy. Yeah. So it just boils down now to prioritization.

Like we prioritize like what parts of that particular gem, like how big is the vulnerability? And you know how the components that it touches. Are they critical parts that we need to be worried and drop everything now and attend to it? Or is it something that we can say?

Yeah, well, we'll deal with it when we do a major upgrade. But yeah.

Speaker 1

And what recommendations do you have for people using open source software or free open source software dependencies for dependency management so that we can mitigate supply chain attacks.

Speaker 2

I think being proactive, we can automate a lot of things in any way, but I think it's the mentality of the engineer that has to be shaped to be proactive with security. I think for me, it's I'm paranoid first. That's my approach, just be paranoid.

Funny enough, there's a gem called paranoid in Ruby's. But yes, I think someone had the same thinking as well, that just be paranoid about anything. But yes, just being very mindful of the code that she introduced.

Yes, depend on what is there, but there are certain things that we should be careful about. The gems, not every implementation in your system can be solved by a gem out there. Sometimes it's also much safer to write stuff yourself, that you can maintain stuff that you can understand and you can control the evolution of it.

Like we say, some of the problems we have in the open source community, it's abandonment of projects, lack of funding, you know the unfortunate events that the maintainers they pass away because it was a sole maintainer.

In such cases it leaves you very vulnerable because either you don't have time for you to do your rewrite at that particular time. So being mindful during the architecture designs of the stuff that you put into your project, any third parties that you put into project.

I think that is very key. So the mentality of the engineers itself has to be. That's what needs to be worked on. Then everything else, it's just a bonus there. Automations that we have, any other services that we can plug into our applications to filter out the dependencies, the vulnerabilities, and all of that. But if we're not intentional and mindful about what we do, we'll still fall back to being attacked.

Speaker 1

And one last question. Does Ruby on Rails itself use a lot of dependencies outside or they tend to write things themselves?

Speaker 2

So the framework itself, it's evolving into, they're calling it the one man or one person framework. The idea being a lot of things can be done within the framework itself.

I'll give you an example with authentication. In the previous versions, there was a heavy dependency on an external gem for authentication, which handled pretty much, I think, I would say for any MVP, it was 100% of the authentication would be handled by that.

But the newer versions, they now have some built-in authentication system that you can just spin up from within the framework. So I would say slowly as the framework is evolving, It's trying to make the dependencies a lot slimmer so that the framework itself doesn't depend too much on anything outside. It then forces you to reevaluate the things that you put in. Like, is it really necessary?

Have I stretched the framework to its limit that it cannot do this particular thing, that I have to end onto something else. But not everyone is running on the latest versions, most people are running the older versions.

So, yes, it does have a heavy dependency on external libraries that don't come with the framework itself. For instance, in the open science community that we do, we work with a lot of different file types that don't get supported natively by Ruby.

So you have to rely on getting external libraries that, you know, support those particular file types and all of that.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much for taking the time to be part of this interview. I don't know if you have anything that you might want to end.

Speaker 2

No, I don't have anything to add. Thank you. It was a pleasure.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much.

Speaker 2

Awesome.